

MECHANICAL PERFORMANCE OF COMPRESSION MOLDED AND INJECTION MOLDED BLENDS OF LARC POLYIMIDE WITH POLYETHERIMIDE (PEI)

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SUMMARY: Two high temperature polyimides from NASA-Langley, LaRC-SI and LaRC-IAX, were injection molded into tensile coupon shapes. A custom injection die was developed with built-in electric heaters to generate the required die temperatures. LaRC-SI and LaRC-IAX tensile coupons were produced by both injection molding and compression molding for performance comparison. Compression molding and injection molding yielded similar mechanical performance. However, non-optimal processing conditions and contamination reduced strength and strain to failure in some specimens. To evaluate trade-offs in blending LaRC-SI and LaRC-IAX with lower cost thermoplastics, PEI blends were studied, prepared by both compression and injection molding. Overall, mechanical properties followed a rule of mixtures relationship, with variations resulting from non-optimal processing rather than blending. Preliminary thermal analysis highlighted extremely different blending related to process conditions. Compression molding resulted in a binary polymeric system while injection molding resulted in a single, completely mixed phase.

KEYWORDS: LaRC-SI, LaRC-IAX, PEI, polyimide thermoplastic, injection molding

INTRODUCTION

Two high temperature thermoplastics, LaRC-SI and LaRC-IAX, have recently been developed by NASA-Langley. These aromatic polyimides exhibit high strength and a high glass transition temperature (240°C), and have been identified for use as adhesives, films and composite matrix material [1]. Composite processing has already been demonstrated, particularly in prepregs of IM7 [2,3] Additional features of both LaRC-SI and LaRC-IAX include good chemical and oxidation resistance and high dielectric strength.

Thus far, LaRC-SI and LaRC-IAX, in powder form, have been successfully compression molded. However, compression molding can be a limiting and high cost manufacturing process. This fact, plus the high cost of LaRC-SI and LaRC-IAX limits the materials' applicability. Injection molding of these polyimides is thus of interest as a significant improvement in manufacturing potential. This paper discusses the results of preliminary injection molding trials with LaRC polyimides from pelletized stock.

To further increase the viability of this material, both LaRC-SI and LaRC-IAX have been blended with ULTEM 1000, an amorphous polyetherimide (PEI) with a glass transition temperature of 212°C. PEI is currently much less expensive than LaRC, yet with comparable

physical properties and only slightly reduced mechanical performance. Blending of these thermoplastics has therefore been investigated as a way to increase the economy of LaRC-SI and LaRC-IAX.

Tensile tests were undertaken to investigate the effects of both processing method and PEI blend ratio on the mechanical performance of LaRC-SI and LaRC-IAX. To investigate the presence of any thermal degradation, as well as the degree of mixing of PEI with each LaRC polyimide, differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) traces of specimens produced by both compression and injection molding are presented.

EXPERIMENTAL

Compression Molding of LaRC-SI, LaRC-IAX and Blends with PEI

Compression molding of LaRC-SI/PEI and LaRC-IAX/PEI blends was carried out with a 20 ton hot press. Powders of LaRC-SI and LaRC-IAX were used to produce all compression molded specimens. At the time of this study, PEI was not available as a powder. Sheets of PEI were therefore milled into small flakes, and dry blends of the thermoplastics were well mixed. Unfortunately, this process of milling PEI introduced impurities which, after molding, resulted in stress concentrating defects in some tensile coupons.

Compression molding of all blends was carried using process parameters obtained with past experience compression molding LaRC-SI. To produce blends with good consolidation and no thermal degradation, a processing temperature of 320°C was used. An aluminum die with a 63.5 mm x 177.8 mm x 25.4 mm cavity was used to prepare all specimens. The resulting 63.5 mm x 177.8 mm sample was subsequently machined into three separate ASTM D-638 type #1 tensile coupons. Machined specimen edges were sanded to eliminate machining induced surface flaws.

Injection Molding of LaRC-SI, LaRC-IAX and Blends with PEI

A two-ton injection molder was used to investigate the injection molding potential for LaRC-SI and LaRC-IAX. The molder, pictured in figure 1, was a screw injector with individual temperature control of the hopper, preheat, screw, nozzle and mold zones.

Figure 1: Two-ton injection molder at CSU

All process zones in the molder are capable of temperatures approaching 400°C, which were found to be necessary to mold these high temperature thermoplastics, except for the water heated mold, which has a maximum temperature near 100°C. To prevent freezing at the mold,

a steel die was custom modified with electric cartridge heaters to enable mold temperatures above 220°C. The geometry of the die cavity was milled to ASTM D-638-89 type #1 tensile coupon specifications, with the exception of a draft angle milled into the cavity walls to facilitate part ejection.

As moisture absorption is an ongoing concern in injection molding plastics, all pellet blends were dried in a recycling desiccant hopper at 140°C for at least 15 hours just prior to injection molding. A given blend ratio was determined to be successfully molded once 20 specimens with good quality, consistency and reasonable absence of contaminants were continuously produced. This procedure allowed the investigation of a variety of blend ratios, from 0% polyimide to 100% polyimide (by volume) in 25% increments, with the limited quantity of LaRC-SI and LaRC-IAX at hand. A portion of the over 200 tensile coupons test coupons produced are pictured in figure 2. Three specimens were produced for each material, blend ratio and processing method combination. That is, a given blend specimen was produced by both compression molding and injection molding for process comparison.

Tensile Testing

Tensile tests were performed at room temperature (25°C) with an ATS universal tester fitted with wedge lock grips. In some cases the grip sections of the tensile coupons were roughened to prevent slippage in the grips. A load rate of 5 mm/min was used in all tests, as per ASTM standard D-638. A clip gage extensometer with a 25.4 mm gage length was used to measure strain. Stress and stiffness for each coupon were calculated based upon the average gage thickness, which generally varied less than 0.05 mm across a given gage section.

Figure 2: LaRC-SI and LaRC-IAX tensile test specimens

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC)

Of great interest is the effect of processing method and conditions on the resulting blend of PEI with LaRC-SI or LaRC-IAX. In particular, the degree of mixing of the two constituents, investigated by looking at changes in glass transition temperature, gives an initial indication of blend quality. To investigate processing effects, two samples were prepared and tested with a Seiko DSC 220C analyzer, one sample taken from an injection molded sample and one from a compression molded sample. Each sample was scraped with a razor blade from the grip section of a 50% LaRC-SI, 50% PEI coupon after tensile testing.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Both LaRC-IAX and LaRC-SI, as well as blends with PEI, were successfully injection molded. Further, blends were found to retain the strength of the neat polymers, indicating the miscibility of the two constituents. A significant amount of data scatter was obtained, however, and is attributed to premature failures in some of the specimens. Typical problems in injection molded specimens included splay marks, white streaks and incomplete cavity fill. These problems can be related to the inability to fully optimize processing parameters such as temperature and pressure with the limited material at hand. Compression molded specimens were far more consistent in their quality, due to extensive processing experience with LaRC polyimides. Contamination was a significant problem for both processing methods, however, and was generally intermittent and unpredictable.

LaRC-SI blends exhibited greater ductility and toughness than LaRC-IAX blends. LaRC-SI blends were characterized by plastic flow associated with neck down, while LaRC-IAX blends were almost exclusively brittle in their fracture behavior. For the process parameters employed, the stress-strain behaviors observed in these materials are shown in figure 3 (a and b), which can be considered representative of mechanical behavior of LaRC-SI and LaRC-IAX.

Figure 3 (a & b): Relative stress-strain performance of LaRC-SI and LaRC-IAX

Higher failure strengths were usually obtained with LaRC-SI than with LaRC-IAX. The highest ultimate tensile stresses obtained with LaRC-IAX blends were 110-115 MPa, while in LaRC-SI blends was 135 MPa. However, as seen in figure 3, the failure strength of

LaRC-IAX is similar to the yield point of LaRC-SI. LaRC-SI blends thus appear to be roughly 10-20% stronger, although this reduction may originate from reduced flaw sensitivity.

LaRC-SI/PEI Blend Tensile Tests

Figure 4 relates the elastic modulus and ultimate tensile strength of LaRC-SI blends with PEI to the blend composition. Based on investigations of specimen failure mode, it was observed that low strength specimens failed prematurely at a point defect or impurity. Figure 4 thus shows the best performance obtained for each blend ratio, as these results are considered the most accurate assessment of the material.

Figure 4: Elastic modulus and ultimate tensile strength vs. blend ratio for LaRC-SI/PEI

The strength of injection molded and compression molded LaRC-SI blends are very similar, indicating no strength tradeoff with injection molding. For each processing method, as the volume percent of LaRC-SI increases, the ultimate tensile strength increases in a linear fashion, from 110 MPa to over 130 MPa. Injection molded specimen modulus is consistently lower than the corresponding modulus of compression molded specimens. The origin of this difference is unclear, although it is less than 10% in most cases.

LaRC-IAX/PEI Blend Tensile Tests

Figure 5 relates the elastic modulus and ultimate tensile strength in LaRC-IAX blends with PEI to blend composition in the same manner as figure 4. No clear trend in ultimate tensile strength is apparent with respect to blend composition in either compression or injection molded LaRC-IAX specimens. Blends of LaRC-IAX failed in a predominantly brittle fashion (recall figure 3a), and impurities had a significant effect on the ultimate strength due to flaw sensitivity. It should also be noted that the semi-crystalline nature of LaRC-IAX may have

played a role in making the generation of consistent blends more difficult than with LaRC-SI, which is amorphous. Further, the injection molding process was not as well optimized as with LaRC-SI, and so specimens of acceptable quality were more difficult to achieve.

Figure 5: Elastic modulus and ultimate tensile strength vs. blend ratio for LaRC-IAX/PEI

Injection molded specimen modulus, shown in figure 5, is consistently lower than the corresponding modulus of compression molded specimens, just as in figure 4. The difference between the two processing methods is again less than 10% in most cases. The general trend is a slight increase in modulus as the amount of LaRC-IAX is increased. Data roughly follow a rule of mixtures relationship, with no significant deviations.

Differences Between Compression Molded and Injection Molded Specimens

Compression and injection molding processes resulted in blends with similar yet highly scattered mechanical performance. Failures outside the gage section (indicating brittleness and high flaw sensitivity) were more prevalent in compression molded specimens. This is related to the presence of contaminants in the milled PEI prior to processing, which introduced defects and provides an explanation for the increased number of failures outside the gage length. Some injection molded specimens failed in this fashion, also at point defects related to contaminants. An example of an out-of-gage failure is seen in figure 6, a cross sectional micrograph of an internal flaw generated fracture surface in a 25% LaRC-IAX, 75% PEI injection molded part. The flaw is located at the center of the image.

All samples were observed to have elastic moduli in the range 3.2-3.7 GPa. Changes in modulus did not correlate with ultimate tensile strength. Failure strain, however, was clearly observed to increase with strength, as one would intuitively expect based on a Hookean relationship between stress and strain, given a more or less constant modulus.

Figure 6: Cross-section micrograph of brittle fracture surface generated by internal flow outside gage section. Specimen is 25% LaRC-IAX, 75% PEI, injection molded.

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC)

Figure 7 and 8 show traces generated by DSC analysis of compression and injection molded specimens, respectively. Figure 7 shows two distinct "dips" in the DSC trace, one located at the T_g of PEI (212°C) and one at the T_g of LaRC-SI (239°C). The sample thus contains both polymer species, as separate phases rather than an actual blend. Note in figure 8, however, that in the injection molded specimen there is only one intermediate glass transition occurring, at 225°C. This indicates complete mixing of the two species, and the creation of a miscible blend of PEI and LaRC-SI. Thus, the compression and injection molding processes seem to produce blends that are fundamentally different. This difference may be due to the increased mixing, as well as the higher temperature and pressure of injection molding.

Figure 7: DSC trace of 50% LaRC-SI, 50% PEI compression molded specimen

Figure 8: DSC trace of 50% LaRC-SI, 50% PEI injection molded specimen

CONCLUSIONS

Both LaRC-SI and LaRC-IAX polyimides have been successfully injection molded into ASTM type #1 tensile coupons. Mechanical performance of these injection molded coupons compares favorably to compression molded specimens of LaRC-SI and LaRC-IAX. The polyimides have also been successfully blended with PEI and found to retain mechanical properties while significantly reducing the quantity of the thermoplastic polyimide.

Contamination and non-optimized processing have limited the mechanical performance observed in all blends. These conditions contributed to premature failures of a number of specimens during tensile testing. Further, it was found with differential scanning calorimetry that the compression molding parameters resulted in specimens which were essentially two phase materials, while injection molded specimens were completely blended.

Future efforts involving LaRC-SI/PEI and LaRC-IAX/PEI blends should involve commercial PEI powders to eliminate contamination, and optimization of injection molding parameters. Also, in-depth thermal analysis is planned to evaluate the various blends and changing process conditions. Finally, testing of non-mechanical performance of such blends is also necessary since one of the principal strengths of the high temperature thermoplastic polyimides is chemical resistance.

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